

**CULTURE, IMAGINATION AND REPRESENTATION: THE WOMAN
IN SELECTED YORUBA THERAPEUTIC INCANTATIONS**

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Abstract

Women, otherwise called ‘Mothers’ (*Ayé*) in many indigenous Yoruba narratives, songs and verses, are represented in diverse imageries that project them as the good, the bad and the ugly. Whereas women are largely perceived to have more negative traits, this study examined the benign image of women in its contribution to the delivery of health and protection in the culture of the Yoruba people. This study adopted Durkheim’s Structural Functionalism theory, which posits that every aspect of the people’s folklore works to reinforce its overall functionality towards achieving societal stability. This theory assisted the conduct of the content analysis of the different references to women in the verses of incantation. The selected Yoruba therapeutic incantations, purposively gathered through ethnographic fieldwork, made use of the image of women based on mythical assumptions that they have magical potential through which things could be made to happen or not to happen. The names which are coded were combined with formulas that are used to reinforce the processes of conception, birth and protection. It is evinced through this study that there is hardly any exclusive traditional Yoruba male group or role in which a woman’s presence is not required. This study concluded that, although seemingly invisible, women are

mostly indispensable in the practices that they feature, suggesting the illogicality in claiming that the African culture is not gender sensitive.

Keywords: Incantations, Representation, Structural Functionalism, Women, Yoruba Culture

Introduction

There is no doubt that the traditional patriarchal perception of the woman as a member of the African society is anything but salutary. As a presumed 'free' member of society, she is constrained, repressed, subjected, denied, objectified, misinterpreted and utterly slighted (Smith, 1990; Beauvoir, 1949; Walby, 1990). The woman remains constrained in a patriarchy because her roles, as a member of the society, are predetermined and fixed to the extent that there are acceptable standards of behaviour she must adhere to for her to be considered virtuous and decent; she is repressed because she must remain in the background, unheard and unseen at family gatherings unless her presence is required, otherwise which she could be considered disrespectful, intrusive and unduly forward (Amadiume, 1987; Nnaemeka, 1998). The subjection of the woman places her under so many monitoring and control agents both within and outside the marriage precinct, such that her marriage becomes endangered based on a malicious report by an unfriendly individual; she is also always denied her right as a wife and her possession as a mother (Oyěwùmí, 1997; Kandiyoti, 1988). In most patriarchal setups, the woman does not own property, and her children belong to the husband, whose name they all adopt as a confirmation of being their owner (Tamale, 2006; Aina, 1998). Moreover, the patriarchy considers the woman a chattel whose fate is determined by her owner, admired for being available for such services as sex, baby making, baby care, cooking, laundry, and so on (Hooks, 2000; Lerner, 1986). Some men, in fact, go to the extreme by not allowing their wives to engage in any profitable enterprise, claiming that what they want is a 'full-time' housewife (Walby, 1990; Aina, 1998).

The misrepresentation of women in most patriarchal societies originated from the mysteries surrounding their existence. These mysteries include her ability for secrecy, conception of pregnancy, gestating the foetus and birthing of the baby, all of which combine to reinforce the prodigious image of the woman

(Amadiume, 1987; Ortner, 1974). Her efforts and accomplishments are therefore not always considered to be the results of her resilience but attainments through certain strange influences (Nnaemeka, 1998). The slighting of the woman in a patriarchal society comes in many forms, of which the most obvious is seen in her being regarded as 'the other' and the inferior (Beauvoir, 1949; Spivak, 1988). As the other, she is disparaged in most proverbs of the people. Some patriarchal cultural sayings are known to create the feeling that it is wrong to have only female children (Awe, 1992; Oyěwùmí, 1997). In Yoruba culture, for example, the proverb that, *Kàkà kó sà̀n fún ìyá àjé níṣe ló fì gbogbo ọ̀mọ̀ rẹ̀ bí obìnrin, ẹ̀yẹ wá ńyí lu ẹ̀yẹ* (Rather than things getting better for the witch-mother she births all-female children, birds keep multiplying), thus giving the impression that it is only women who are witches. Whereas experiences have shown, from the coinage of *Àjékùnrin* (Male-witch), that witches are also found among men in African societies, even then, the roles they are believed to play are debatable and possibly a subject for another discourse (Drewal & Drewal, 1983).

Another instance in which the woman is slighted in African society is regarding her status as a member of the family. As a girl-child, male children are privileged over her; as a wife, she remains subservient to the husband; and as a mother, the woman plays the inferior role or any other allowed her by the patriarchy (Oyěwùmí, 1997; Tamale, 2006). In fact, being a closed unit, the family group affords an examination of the subservient roles of the woman for whom the use of personal initiative is unacceptable (Lerner, 1986; Walby, 1990). In most cases, the status of the male children born to the same woman is greater than hers, and she is obliged to defer to all male children, even those who are younger than her own male children within the family (Amadiume, 1987). She may sometimes also not be allowed to call any male child, except her own children, by their real names; she could only call them by appellations, possibly created by her or any other senior wife (Awe, 1992; Nnaemeka, 1998).

This study is restricted to the examination of women's social, physical, and spiritual roles in conception, pregnancy, and childbirth within the African cultural context. It does not attempt a general analysis of all aspects of women's experiences in African society but focuses specifically on how these reproductive and maternal roles shape the image and perception of women.

Literature Review

The assertion that most traditional African societies are patriarchal in nature is a long-held one. This is because in most cultures in Africa, such practices are found that make men exercise power and control over women. These cultures are characterized by male dominance, which can be seen in social, political, and legal systems. From the Yoruba in Nigeria, the Igbo in Nigeria, the Masai in Kenya, the Zulu in South Africa, to the Himba in Angola, women do not have any clear-cut functions in society except those auxiliary roles reserved for them by men.

Ebila (2015) discusses the contradictions surrounding the perception, place and identity of women in African (Kenya) politics, exploring how, through Wangari Maathai's *Unbowed*, the patriarchy, represented by some male leaders of postcolonial states, attempts to silence the voices of women politicians by urging them to behave like 'proper women'. The work concludes that some women's writing will be better appreciated if considered as providing the appropriate lens that can be used to view and question the social construction of womanhood versus manhood and the influence on gender power relations on women's participation in the politics of the postcolonial nation-states in Africa.

The examination by Sow (2018) of how women are represented in cultural, religious and political ideologies (systems of ideas) which imagine them, fantasise them or criticise them, either as individual or collective icons, has imposed on women most of the challenges surrounding their identity today. The study concludes that the sociology of the family has renewed the study of its dynamics, its changing types of arrangement, of discussion, of negotiation, of conflictual relations between individuals such that it has become imperative to, more than ever, review the place of women in our societies, from the political hierarchy to grassroots communities, and their access to land, resources, political power, and so on.

Also, reviewing the roles of the woman in the typical traditional African (Kenyan) family is Karani (1987), who contends that such roles as teaching, baby-nursing, providing companionship and support for men, and the like, are fast being abdicated by women, given the modern economic and social realities, thereby creating unnecessary moral gaps in society. The paper concludes that modern

women should always remember their ‘care-giving’ responsibilities to the family rather than running after vanities.

Moreover, Zimon (2006) strongly debates the contentious roles of women in African religion across time, insisting that ethnological and religious studies point to cultural rather than biological differentiation in the status of men and women, thereby considering procreation as the woman’s main vocation and task. Whereas the woman performs the role of a native doctor and healer among many African peoples since the basic medical care takes place within the family, and may sometimes, after menopause, perform priestly duties to a smaller degree, among other important roles. This study concludes that both men and women perform similar roles in sensitive social-religious and spiritual matters, rather than for the woman always to be considered as the inferior gender. Fundamentally, while all the reviewed works align with the scope of this study, Zimon (2006) corroborates it in terms of locating the woman in action beyond the trivial roles and responsibilities reserved for her in the patriarchal African setting.

The discussion of the second-class status and supportive roles of the woman in the patriarchal African setting, according to many pro-feminism discourses, is blamed on the privileged and controlling positions occupied by men across ages. Whereas, the pro-feminists posit that, in a real or genetic sense of it, nothing seems to differentiate the woman and her ability from those of the man, thereby contesting a few biological factors which seem to support the frailty of the woman as rather tenuous. The saying, among Yoruba people, that *È má ẹ̀ ohun orò lójú obìnrin, obìnrin kò ní gògòngò* (Do not let a woman into secret things, the woman has no vocal cords) is a disparaging footnote on the lack of trust in women and the danger of confiding in them. This is simply equating the ability for secret keeping with the protrusion usually found in the anterior position of the neck of a man, but which is lacking in that of a woman. If the fate of biblical Samson for trusting Delilah the wife, was tragic, one cannot help but reconsider the case of Lady Macbeth, who not only supports the husband’s ambition, but also supervises its successful outcome, regardless of the morality involved.

Theoretical Framework

Generally, structural functionalism underscores a societal equilibrium where everything works to sustain the systemic order, and upon which the system keeps adjusting to achieve stability ultimately. Durkheim (2003, p. 52) asserts that

... society should be analyzed and described in terms of functions; it is a system of interrelated parts where no one part can function without the other. These parts make up the whole of society. If one part changes, it has an impact on society as a whole.

In oral literature, Functionalism refers to how traditional oral narratives (such as myths, folktales, legends, and other forms of storytelling) serve specific social functions within a culture, and particularly hinges on the idea that cultural practices, including oral traditions, work together to maintain the structure and stability of society to regulate behaviour, transmit values, and reinforce social cohesion.

To Durkheim, society is to be viewed as an entity in itself, distinguishable from and irreducible to its constituent parts, as cited in Jones (2003) and Alketbi & Altaii (2025), that "...the society... is formed by the structure of the rules of culture, thus the community is submissive and obedient to their beliefs and practices" thereby, agreeing that the oracy of a people functions to reinforce a people's sense of identity of particular group of people. Functional approach, according to Sims and Stephens (2005), is a strategy to discover the meaning of folk practices. As a broad perspective in sociology and anthropology, which interprets society as a structure with interrelated parts, Functionalism addresses the society as a whole in terms of the functions of its constituent elements, such as norms, customs, traditions, institutions, names, and so on. Function as intended is distinguished from "purpose" or "use" because it does not presuppose any conscious or deliberate intention in bringing about effects. In the current study, functionalism will help to discover the meaning associated with specific images of women and how such names function within the folk incantations of the Yoruba people.

Methodology

Four purposively selected Yoruba therapeutic incantations were used in this study. The incantations were selected based on their reflection of the images, names and epithets of women as subjects or objects of certain actions. The verses, partly recorded from an oral delivery by willing indigenous Yoruba Onisegun (Healers) and partly adapted from Fabunmi (1972), were translated into English for ease of understanding. The selected incantations comprised those used for

protection, commerce, and birth delivery. Both the Yoruba versions and English translations of the verses of incantations have been placed side by side in a table for ease of interpretation and analysis. The study adopted a qualitative research method through which the functionality of the highlighted images and nomenclatures is revealed.

Presentation and Discussion of Data

In the analysis to be conducted here, the Yoruba version of the incantations and the English translation are placed side by side in a table in order to aid their adequate understanding. Only four incantations are selected, and these are verses that are used as *aṣàbò* (protection), for *oyún níní* (conception), for *abíwéré* (easy delivery), and, as *awórò* (patronage booster). The first incantatory piece to be examined for its woman-image content is one meant for recovery from unknown diseases. It is meant to protect from the danger of sudden death:

i)	Aṣààbò	Protective
Line	Yoruba	Translation
1	<i>Òyèkú logbè! 3x</i>	<i>Òyèkú logbè! 3x</i>
2	<i>Kí ó rin gbangba yekú rẹ láwọn ọ́tá rẹ lóri</i>	Do walk openly to avenge your death onto your enemies' heads
3	<i>Òyèkú logbè! Òyèkú logbè! Òyèkú logbè!</i>	<i>Òyèkú logbè! Òyèkú logbè! Òyèkú logbè!</i>
4	<i>Kí ó rin kòkò yekú rẹ láwọn ọ́tá rẹ lóri</i>	Do walk furtively to avert your death onto your enemies' heads
5	<i>Nítorí ojó tí làgìdì bá fojú kan iyámòpó</i>	Because the day <i>lagidi</i> sets his eyes on <i>iyámòpó</i>
6	<i>Ojó nàà ló máa da tawó rẹ sílè</i>	That day, it submitted all in its possession
7	<i>Ojó tí ewúré bá bímọ tiẹ ní ń dide</i>	The day a nanny-goat gives birth to its kid, does the kid stand up
8	<i>Ojó tí àgùntàn bá bímọ tiẹ ní ń dide</i>	The day an ewe gives birth to her kid, does the kid stand up
9	<i>Ojó tí lèkélèké bá bímọ tiẹ ní ń rìn</i>	The day a female cow-egret

		gives birth to its kid, does the kid walk
10	<i>Àbàwón àşẹ lóri iwọ lágbájá ọmọ lágbájá</i>	Authority proclaimed on you so-so child of so-so
11	<i>Báyìì báyìì òun ni kí ó jí dídè</i>	To immediately now awake and rise up
12	<i>Tó!</i>	So shall it be!

The particular lines of the incantation which allude to the woman are 5-10. In the 5th line, that reference is euphemistically achieved with the use of the name *Ìyámòpó*. The significance of the female name in this context is synecdochical as it refers to the female genitalia, which is set in a binary relation with that of the male referred to in the verse as *Lagidi*. The nexus between the two organs, which literally suggests a copulation act, is connotatively exploited here to foster a sense of compelled or forcible submission of valuables (*da tọwó rẹ sílẹ̀*) to the former. This compelled or forcible submission is what, in turn, commands the loosening of the clutch of the spirit of ailment and death over the life of the supplicant or the client so s/he would have the health restored. Other references made to the woman in this incantation draw upon inferences that only female entities are recognised for, that is, as capable of directly reproducing their likes and, therefore, locating parallel woman-image in the likes of *ewúré* (nanny-goat) line 7, *àgùntàn* (ewe) Line 8 and *abo-lèkélèké* (female cattle egret) line 9. In these parallels, both the reproduction and renewal characteristics of the woman on the one hand are explored, while on the other hand, the instantaneous energising of after-birth conditions of the kids of the named creatures is explored in the hope of quickening the supplicant's or the client's recovery and protection.

The next incantation in which the image of women is amply reflected is that which could be used to make a woman easily conceive or have a pregnancy. It could also help to ensure the safety of both the mother and the pregnancy throughout the gestation stages.

ii)	Oyun-Nini	Easeful Conception
Line	Yoruba	Translation
1	<i>Ọ̀tòtò n tòrò</i>	Distinctive is the word

2	<i>Òtòtò là á jèpà</i>	Distinctively, does one eat the groundnut
3	<i>Òtòtò là á jèmumu</i>	Distinctively, does one eat the tiger nut
4	<i>Adifá fún òrò iwásè</i>	As divined for the primeval word
5	<i>Tí n se ipilè ohun gbogbo</i>	That is the foundation of creation
6	<i>Ó wá sọ báyii wí pé:</i>	It thus pronounces that
7	<i>Ká mú ǹnkan torí torí</i>	We take something by the head
8	<i>Ká mú ǹnkan t̀r̀un t̀r̀un</i>	We take something by the neck
9	<i>Ká mú ǹnkan lódindi lódindi</i>	We take something in its whole.
10	<i>Ká r̀è é fún Ọbamakin tí ǹ b̀è lókè r̀òjé</i>	And take it to Ọbamakin on Ìr̀òjé hill
11	<i>KỌbamakin l̀è fún wa ní ǹnkan lódindi lódindi</i>	So that Ọbamakin may give something to us in fullness.
12	<i>Nitori, atóróró lorúkọ à ǹ pokó</i>	For one, One-long-stick is the name the penis is called
13	<i>Ìlù kan dùgbè lorúkọ à ǹ pòbò</i>	One-monstrous-drum is the name we call the vagina
14	<i>Èèwò òrìsà!</i>	It is utterly forbidden!
15	<i>Emọ k̀ì í wáyé kó má bí</i>	No rodent comes to life without procreating
16	<i>Àtọlè dọlè là á bá nínú àdán</i>	It is generations of foetuses that are met in a bat's womb
17	<i>Kí ọlè ayò kí ó sọ nínú ilémọ lágbájá omọ lágbájá</i>	May a joyful foetus spring in the womb of so-so, the child of so-so (mother's name)
18	<i>Tó! 3ce</i>	So shall it be! 3ce

There are different images of women generously spread across this incantation, some of which constitute direct references, while others are not. The first of such images, in line 13, which is 'synecdochical' with the description of the female reproductive organ, *òbò* (vagina) as a monstrous drum whose drumstick or beater, mentioned in the preceding line, *okó* (penis), is meant to activate both the principal and the ancillary agents of reproduction, using their essential names. It is

the belief in Yoruba culture that things are represented in their code names, which, when mentioned, trigger them into action. In the context of this incantation, therefore, the role of the woman as the primary agent of reproduction is hardly debatable. The woman remains the host for pregnancy.

Other referents that could be considered as paralleling the image of the woman in the incantation due to their pregnancy-carrying ability include *emó* (rodent) and *àdán* (bat). Because both of these organisms are known for carrying multiple pregnancies and birthing multiple pups, they affirm or advance the desire of the supplicant or the target, who is more likely to be a woman. As a kind of confirmation of the gender of the supplicant or the target, the biological organ for gestation of offspring before birth, *ilé-omo* (womb), mentioned in line 17, is an indirect reference to the woman. Therefore, for the prayer of the supplicant for pregnancy and birth to come to fruition, the presence of the woman as a mediator is incontestable.

Coming next is an incantation that aids the easy delivery of pregnancy in women. It helps to eliminate all manners of complications in the process of birthing pregnancy, particularly where some negative forces are suspected to be at work.

iii) *Abíwéré*

Easy-Delivery

Line	Yoruba	English Translation
1	<i>Oyíndàólá omọ Èrìòsèjè! 3ce</i>	Oyíndàólá the offspring of Èrìòsèjè! 3ce
2	<i>A gbọ pé o bímọ</i>	We learnt you gave birth to a baby
3	<i>Ó ní bèè ni</i>	She said it is true
4	<i>Şùgbọn ẹnì kankan kò gbọ rířbí rẹ</i>	But no one heard you were in labour
5	<i>Ó ní ogbọ ló ní kí wọn máa gbọ</i>	She said it is ogbo that commands that they should not hear
6	<i>Ó ní imọ ló ní kí wọn máa mọ</i>	She said it is imo that commands that they should not know
7	<i>Èmi lámọyín omọ lámọyín</i>	I so-so the child of so-so

		(mother's name)
8	<i>Oyún tí mo ní yìí</i>	I am carrying this pregnancy
9	<i>Lójó tí mo bá máa bímọ</i>	The day I will be delivered of it
10	<i>Kí eku ilé kí ó má gbọ</i>	May the rat in the house not hear
11	<i>Kí aáyán ilé kí ó má mọ</i>	May the cockroach in the house not hear
12	<i>Kí n bímọ kẹni roko tó dé</i>	May I give birth before those who go to the farm return?
13	<i>Kí n bímọ kẹni rodò tó bọ</i>	May I give birth before those who go to the river return
14	<i>Kí wón má fòbẹ gbọmọ jáde nínú mi</i>	May they not use a knife to deliver me of the baby
15	<i>Tí n bá ti n forúnkún ọtún kúnlẹ</i>	When I kneel with the right leg
16	<i>Kí n máa fi tòsi òdè</i>	May I stand up with the left leg?
17	<i>Kí omi má pọ̀jù</i>	May there be no excessive birth fluid
18	<i>Kí èjẹ má ṣaláitò lójó náà</i>	May there be no blood shortage that day
19	<i>Ááṣẹ!</i>	So shall it be!

This poem reflects the image of women in many respects. Beginning from the first line, it shows that the incantation is for women and about women because the names mentioned, *Oyíndàólá* and *Èrìòsẹ̀jẹ̀*, are feminine: the first as the child and the second, the mother. *Oyíndàólá* the child is an archetypal figure for every pregnant woman hoping to go into labour and return unscathed, bringing her child home safely too, so that, according to the prayer of Yoruba people, ...*kí a gbọ̀hùn ìyá kí a gbọ̀hùn ọmọ* (...so we may hear the voice of the mother and the newly born), praying for the safety of the mother and child. The rationale behind the mentioning of the name of the mother is informed by the belief among the Yoruba people that the connection between a child (male or female) can never be doubted, unlike the relationship with the father, therefore, making the mother a more reliable medium to connect the child either for positive or negative purposes. The name *Oyíndàólá*, in this circumstance, could be translated as “assortment-of-sweetness-and-wealth” (sweetness represented in honey and wealth, the child).

This position is supported by the Yoruba saying that, ...*omọ kò şeé fowó rà* (...a child cannot be bought with money). In both cases here, the woman is seen as a quester or supplicant as well as a supporter or life-saver.

Beyond being always made to be seen in negative lights, women have their own share of problems confronting them in their lived lives, like any mortal, and this is attested to by some other references to her in the text. These could be found in lines 2, 4, 8, 9, 14, 15 & 16, 17 & 18 of the incantation and are explainable as follows:

In line 2, her inalienable duty as the only one capable of birthing a child and on whose sanctioning the man relies for him to own a family; line 4 reveals the woman’s lonely, tortuous and darkest moments of the labour-room ritual where and when she gets the child; line 8 speaks about the moment of gestation and her own transformation; line 9, her own expectations and apprehension, line 14, breaking her apprehension with supplication; line 15 and 16, the complementary positions anticipating a successful birthing of a child. In the Yoruba traditional birth attendance practice, women in labour are made to remain on their knees at the moment the child will emerge in order to lessen the gravitational pull of the cervix while paving the way for the expansion of the pelvis, and thereby easing the easy passage of the baby. That done, the woman is expected to rise with the left limb – showing strength and recovery. That anticipated complementarity is always expressed as a prayer for an expectant mother among Yoruba people that, ...*bí o bá ti ñ forúnkún òtún kúnlẹ̀ ni kí o máa forúnkún òsì dide* (...as you kneel with the right limb so shall you rise using the left knee); and lines 17 & 18 present another complementarity bordering on anticipated state of equilibrium in the measured supply of the two bodily life supporting fluids- blood and water, so that none is either in excess or short supply, for the avoidance of fatality.

The next incantation is a dedicated verse of a female deity named *Obinřen-Òjòwú* (The Envious Mother), worshipped by the indigenous Ijebu-Ode people. It is believed to be capable of blessing people with wealth and children.

iv)	<i>Ìbùkún</i>	Blessing
Line	<i>Yoruba</i>	English Translation
1	<i>Tẹ̀lú tẹ̀lú awo Ègbá</i>	Tẹ̀lú Tẹ̀lú is the initiate of Ègbá
2	<i>Tẹ̀lú tẹ̀lú awo òde-Ìjẹ̀sà</i>	Tẹ̀lú Tẹ̀lú is the initiate of Ìjẹ̀sà

		town
3	<i>Òun nàà ní í sawo nílè Oòduà</i>	It is the same that is the initiate in the home of Oòduà
4	<i>Kẹ̀lẹ̀mbú ní í sawo Ọ̀lọ̀wá</i>	Kẹ̀lẹ̀mbú is the initiate of Ọ̀lọ̀wá
5	<i>Àwọn ló dífá fún Ọ̀lọ̀wá lòde Imòrìsà</i>	It was who divined for Ọ̀lọ̀wá in Ọ̀de's shrine of the deity
6	<i>Tí wọn ní kí ó lọ fẹ̀bọ̀ lẹ̀lẹ̀ lẹ̀nu ọ̀nà</i>	It instructed that he place a sacrifice at the entrance
7	<i>Kí ó sì sawo ẹ̀nu</i>	And also initiate into the fraternity of the mouth.
8	<i>Ó wá béèrè wí pé awo wo lawo ẹ̀nu</i>	He then asked what the fraternity of the mouth was
9	<i>Wọn ní awo agbó awo atọ̀ lawo ẹ̀nu</i>	He was told that it is the fraternity of aging and lasting.
10	<i>Ọ̀lọ̀wá wá di ẹ̀ni lómọ̀ ó di ẹ̀ni lówó</i>	Thus, Ọ̀lọ̀wá became the owner of many children and the owner of wealth
11	<i>Torí nàà, ẹ̀ni forí balẹ̀ fún yín, á gbó</i>	Therefore, whoever is obedient to you will age
12	<i>Ẹ̀ni forí balẹ̀ fún yín, á tọ̀</i>	Whoever is obedient to you will last.
13	<i>Ẹ̀ni forí balẹ̀ fún yín á bí wẹ̀ré</i>	Whoever is obedient to you will have easy delivery
14	<i>Ẹ̀ jòwọ̀ ẹ̀ jẹ̀ kí lágbájá ọ̀mọ̀ lágbájá bí wẹ̀ré 3ce</i>	Please, do let so-so the child of so-so give birth with ease 3ce
15	<i>Tó! Tó! Tó!</i>	So shall it be! 3ce

Beyond the fact that this incantation is dedicated to a female deity who watches over a female cult, which women predominantly attend, but whose priest is named *Ọ̀lọ̀wá-Ìbẹ̀rù* (Owner of the Dreaded-Shrine). However, a man must go through life dressing like a woman, plaiting his hair, tying wrappers and keeping away from rites forbidden to women- such as sighting *Oro*³ and *Agemọ*⁴, it has, by a similar token, several allusions made to women. The first of such references could

³ This is bull-roarer spirit associate with the Yoruba ancestral worship

⁴ Literally referring to the Chameleon- the cohesive spiritual factor among Ijebu people

be seen in the code name of the deity, *Kèlèmbú*, depicting the female effigy and the power house of the sanctuary, particularly helping women to conceive and have children. This effigy, which remains in seclusion and is scarcely seen all year round except during her celebration days, has a male counterpart- a figurehead- that people always see. That female effigy represents the African Mothers' willpower to grant their children's petitions.

Also serving to refer to women in this incantation are the various Yoruba pronouns in some lines coming after the element discussed in the last paragraph. These could be seen in lines 5, 6 and 9 as variously used in such items as *àwọn/wọn*, all of which approximate the English pronoun "they" and imply, among other qualities, the guild of women's clairvoyant power as guardians, capable of charting the course to prosperity for whosoever they are pleased with. Also, in lines 11, 12 and 13, which exhibit the use of the Yoruba pronoun, *yín* (you), are meant to emphasise the compliant requirement as sine qua non to securing the favours of the mother-force. This aspect of the incantation seems to parallel the popular biblical saying in 1 Sam. 15: 22, which reads partly that "To obey is better than sacrifice, and to heed is better than the fat of rams", also emphasising the importance of heart attitude and obedience over mere outward actions.

Finally, in the 14th line of the incantation, an entreaty to the mothers using the Yoruba collective pronoun, *E*, expandable as *Èyin* or *Gbogbo yín*, whose English parallel could be "you all", alluding to the guild-body, and particularly in the entire line, referring to the mother's ability to sanction prayers. This aspect conforms with several Yoruba cultural sayings which reinforce the mother-child connection including, *Yèyé ọmọ ní ń gbọmọ, irùkẹrẹ ní ń gbọmọ Ọrúnmilà* (The mother comes to the rescue of the child as the *irùkẹrẹ* [horsetail] provides a cuddle for the *Ọrúnmilà* initiate) or *Abiyamọ kan kò ní gbékún ọmọ rẹ kó má tati were* (No nursing mother hears the cry of her baby and will not stop-short).

Coming last among the selected therapeutic incantations in which women are represented for their benevolence and good value is the one below, which is used for courting, attracting or boosting favour or patronage from people, known and unknown.

v) Line	Awórò Yoruba	Patronage Booster Translation
1	<i>Ajikore! Arìnkore! Àrinnàkore!</i>	<i>Ajikore! Arìnkore! Arinnàkore!</i>
2	<i>Ajikore lorúko tí à ñ pe Ifá</i>	<i>Ajikore is the name we call Ifá</i>
3	<i>Arìnkore lorúko tí à ñ pÈṣù òdàrà</i>	<i>Arìnkore is the name we call Èṣù, the mischief maker</i>
4	<i>Àrinnàkore lorúko tí à ñ pe èyin Ìyá mi</i>	<i>Àrinnàkore is the name we call my Earth-Mothers</i>
5	<i>Ò-jí-fààrò-gbégbá-orò-kalè, orúko tí à ñ pe èyin Ajé</i>	<i>Ò-jí-f'ààrò-gbé'gbá-orò-kalè, the name we call Ajé</i>
6	<i>Kí n jí kí n jí kore bí i tlfá</i>	<i>May I wake early and meet with favour like Ifa?</i>
7	<i>Kí n rìn láàárò kí n kore bí tÈṣù Òdàrà</i>	<i>May I stroll out in the morning and meet with favour ike Esu, the mischief maker</i>
8	<i>Kí n jí fèsè rìnnà kore bí tèyin Yeyé</i>	<i>May I walk the road and be fortunate like you Mothers</i>
9	<i>Kí eyè àtàtà mi gbójà kalè kí gbogbo eyè ayé wá náa</i>	<i>May I, like the atata bird, display my goods for all other birds to patronize</i>
10	<i>Tòtún tòsì ni eyélé fì ñ kóre wolé</i>	<i>With both right and left wings, the pigeon (bird) brings in fortune</i>
11	<i>Onibààrà mi àná onibààrà ikàsè ni</i>	<i>My customer of yesterday is a stale one today.</i>
12	<i>È lọ kó onibààrà tuntun repẹte wá fún mi</i>	<i>Go forth and draw new multitudinous customers to me</i>
13	<i>Owó mi àná ó dowó ikàsè lónì</i>	<i>The money I received yesterday is stale today</i>
14	<i>È lọ gbówó tuntun owó ñlá wá fún mi</i>	<i>Go forth and bring in a new and huge amount of money for me.</i>
15	<i>Ajé mi àná ò dajé ikàsè lónì</i>	<i>My sales from yesterday are stale today</i>
16	<i>È lọ gbájé tuntun ajé ñlá wá fún mi</i>	<i>Go and bring in new and huge sales for me.</i>

- 17 *Láti òdò òkúnrin, láti òdò obínrin wá* Fourth from men, from women
 18 *Áti omòdé àti àgbà* Both young and old
 19 *Kí ẹ̀ lọ gbé ire tẹ̀mi wá fún mi lónìì* Let all bring forth my fortune this
 day

Several elements mentioned in this incantation are instrumental to its potency out of which the woman-image stands out prominent and without which the desire of the verse would have failed. The first element which alludes to women as contained in line 6 is a metaphorical name, *Ò-jí-f'àárò-gbé'gbá-orò-kalẹ̀* (s/he who, in the early morning, sets up the platform of wealth), affirming the ability of the mothers to make rich. As one of the terrestrial powers otherwise called *Àjé* (Witches) are supposed to be celebrated and are actually celebrated, particularly through *Gẹ̀lẹ̀dẹ̀* among *Kétu-Ànàgó* in Yoruba land rather than stigmatised, and the release of their full potential enabling healing, progress and prosperity rather than negativity of harm and destruction. It has been argued in some quarters that the “craft” associated with “witch” marks it out as a form of “science” or “know-how” rather than one esoteric, evil or dark cult or enterprise. They are known to stand in the gap for people who do their will and could severely punish whoever offends them. According to Yekinni Ajileye’s *Kòtò Ayé*⁵, the members of the guild of witches pride themselves as, *Àwa tí Ọlórún gbé ayé lé lówó* (We, to whom God handed the affairs of the world), and by inference, are in control of the wealth therein.

In a related vein, there is another reference to women in the 8th line as, *ẹ̀yin Ẹ̀yẹ̀* (you Mothers), referring to the guild, particularly about the unfailing success of their expeditions, for which the supplicant thus prays that: *Kí n jí fẹ̀sẹ̀ rìnnà kore* (May I walk the road and be fortunate). The references in lines 9 & 10 to two different birds, *atata* and *ẹ̀yẹ̀lé*, are symbolic to the extent that the first name projects the act of sales, /a/, /tá/, /tà/ in the last two of its three syllables. All the syllables taken together will mean “we are selling ceaselessly”. In contrast, the second name emphasises an enduring partnership, which is validated by the Yoruba saying that *Ẹ̀yẹ̀lé kò ní bá onílẹ̀ jẹ̀, kó bá onílẹ̀ mu kí ó dojọ̀ ipónjú kó yẹ̀rí* (The pigeon will not wine and dine with its host only to desert them in the face of hardship). Indeed, these birds are generically called *Ẹ̀yẹ̀-ire* (the benevolent bird),

⁵ The Earth-Mother’s dungeon

which is another name for the earth-mothers. These references discussed are furthered in lines 12, 14, 16 & 19, where the mothers are referred to in the Yoruba pronouns, *E* (You) and from whom specific requests are made as follows: *E lo kó onibàárà tuntun repetẹ wá fún mi* (Go forth and draw new multitudinous customers to me); *E lo gbówó tuntun owó ñlá wá fún mi* (Go forth and bring in new and huge amount of money to me); *E lo gbájé tuntun ajé ñlá wá fún mi* (Go and bring in new and huge sales to me), and, *Kí e lo gbé ire tẹmi wá fún mi lóni* (Let all bring forth my fortune this day). Based on the foregoing, women are variously seen as bringers of patronage, bringers of money, bringers of wealth, and bringers of all other goodness, stressing their benevolent orientation.

In the final analysis, the incantation alludes to another undercurrent motif that is central to both the quest and the expected potency of the text, as could be found in almost every line, implying trade, money, patronage, fortune, and the like. In specific terms, the name is mentioned in lines 15 & 16 as *Ajé*, the Yoruba goddess of prosperity and commerce, symbolised with innumerable pure unbroken cowries. Its shrines are found, in whitewash colour, in every communal marketplace in Yoruba land, as it is believed to reside in such a place. There is the popular saying among Yoruba market women that, ...*inú ojà ni Ajé ñ gbé* (...it is in the market place that *Ajé* lives), so when market women haggle prices among themselves, they appeal to the selling party for a reduction, calling the name, *Ajé*. Also, it is customary for Yoruba people across statuses and religions always to pray that, *Ajé má jẹ kí n ní e lórùn, jẹ kí n ní e lówó* (*Ajé* do not let me have you around my neck, let me have you in my palms). Having something around one's neck is to be ensnared by it, while having it in one's palms is to be able to do what one wants with it.

Observations and Conclusion

Observations

The analysis of the selected Yoruba therapeutic incantations reveals that the image of the woman is consistently projected beyond the conventional patriarchal representation of woman as the inferior other. Across the incantations, women are portrayed as indispensable agents in the social, physical, reproductive, economic, and spiritual spheres of life. References to women occur both directly and indirectly through female names, reproductive organs, motherhood, female animals, female deities, symbolic birds, and

collective maternal forces. The texts repeatedly associate women with conception, gestation, childbirth, healing, protection, prosperity, and the continuity of life.

Furthermore, the incantations demonstrate that the efficacy of the therapeutic rites often depends on feminine principles and maternal powers. Whether represented as the biological host of pregnancy, the archetypal mother, the guardian deity, or the collective force of the Earth Mothers (Àjé), women occupy central positions as mediators between the physical and spiritual realms. The analysis therefore suggests that Yoruba incantatory traditions preserve a conception of womanhood that is complementary, powerful, and indispensable to communal well-being.

Conclusion

It could be claimed that most interpretations given to the role of women in Yoruba culture are subjected to patriarchal whims and caprices with the intention of keeping them dominated and subservient. The subversion of the narratives around women, either as mothers or as wives, is calculated to exclude them. However, women know more than men in most of the activities from which they are excluded, such that when men show restraints in discussing the issues in women's presence, the women only let out a chuckle in response. Today in Yoruba land, there exist no exclusively male or female cultural activities anywhere. Men and women globally are daily initiated into what was once culturally cross-gender restrictive circles.

References

- Abraham, R. C. 1958. *Dictionary of modern Yoruba*. London: University of London Press.
- Aina, O. I. (1998). *Women, culture and society*. Amkra Books.
- Alketbi, A. & Altaii, A. (2025). *Structural functional theory and the interpretation of social behavior according to Talcott Parsons and Robert Merton*. *Al-Adab Journal*, (153), 451– 488.
<https://doi.org/10.31973/jbksvt37>
- Amadiume, I. (1987). *Male daughters, female husbands: Gender and sex in an African society*. Zed Books.
- Awe, B. (1992). *Nigerian women in historical perspective*. Sankore Publishers.
- Beauvoir, S. de. (1949/2011). *The second sex*. Vintage Books.

- Drewal, H. J., & Drewal, M. T. (1983). *Gelede: Art and female power among the Yoruba*. Indiana University Press.
- Ebila, F. (2015). 'A proper woman, in the African tradition': *The construction of gender and nationalism in Wangari Maathai's autobiography Unbowed*. *Tydskrif vir Letterkunde*, 52(1), pp.144-145
- Karani, F. A. (1987). The situation and roles of women in Kenya: An overview. *The Journal of Negro Education*, Vol. 56, No. 3.
- Fabunmi, M. A. 1972. *Àyájó ìjìnlẹ̀ ohùn Ifá*. Ibadan: Onibonoje Press.
- Hooks, B. (2000). *Feminism is for everybody: Passionate politics*. South End Press.
- Jones, P. (2003). *Introducing Social Theory*. Polity Press
- Kandiyoti, D. (1988). Bargaining with patriarchy. *Gender & Society*, 2(3), 274–290.
- Lerner, G. (1986). *The creation of patriarchy*. Oxford University Press.
- Nnaemeka, O. (1998). *Sisterhood, feminisms and power: From Africa to the diaspora*. Africa World Press.
- Ortner, S. B. (1974). Is female to male as nature is to culture? *Woman, Culture and Society*, 67-87.
- Oyěwùmí, O. (1997). *The invention of women: Making an African sense of Western gender discourses*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Sims, M. C., & Stephens, M. (2005). *Living Folklore: An Introduction to the Study of People and their Traditions*. Logan, UT: Utah State University Press.
- Smith, B. (1990). *Women and patriarchy in Africa*. African Studies Press.
- Sow, F. (2018). Genre et fondamentalismes. Dakar, Sénégal : CODESRIA.
- Spivak, G. C. (1988). Can the subaltern speak? In *Marxism and the Interpretation of Culture* (pp. 271–313). University of Illinois Press.
- Tamale, S. (2006). *African feminism: How should we change?* Pambazuka Press.
- Walby, S. (1990). *Theorizing patriarchy*. Basil Blackwell.
- Zimoň, H. (2006). *The Role of Women in African Traditional Religions*. *Acta Ethnographica Hungarica*, 51(1-2), 43–60.
<https://doi.org/10.1556/AEthn.51.2006.1-2.3>